

Synthesis of 1:10-Dimethyl-5-Keto- $\Delta^{1:9}$ -Octalin

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An unambiguous synthesis of 1:10-dimethyl-5-keto- $\Delta^{1:9}$ -octalin has been described through the Dieckmann cyclisation of the corresponding cyclohexene derivative. An isomeric mixture of this ketone has been obtained in another synthetic approach.

Synthesis of tri- and tetra-methyldecalones, particularly with *gem*-dimethyl grouping, has recently been described.¹ As a penultimate compound in this series, the synthesis of a dimethyloctalone has been published.² The present investigation reports the synthesis of an isomeric dimethyloctalone (I). There exists, however, in (I) the possibility of introducing the '3-keto' group through allylic oxidation and subsequently the characteristic *gem*-dimethyl grouping through alkylation of the α, β -unsaturated carbonyl function.

The most obvious method appeared to be the condensation of ethyl γ -bromocrotonate with dimethylcyclohexanone and subsequent reduction and dehydration of the product leading to (II) and this on cyclisation was expected to afford (I). The Reformatsky product was found to be a complex mixture from elemental analyses and boiling points of the different fractions isolated on distillation. Next series of attempts may be schematically represented below:

1. Kalvoda *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 40, 2340; Mukherjee *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 67; Narang *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, 2842.

2. Mukherjee, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19B, 94.

Ethyl crotonate underwent the Michael condensation with ethyl acetoacetate to afford the diketo-ester (III) in an excellent yield. This on treatment with phosphorus trichloride³ afforded the unsaturated chloro-ester (IV). On catalytic reduction it afforded the β -ketoester (V), characterised by a deep violet ferric chloride coloration in ethanolic solution. With ethyl γ -bromobutyrate, it afforded (VI) in a moderate yield. Attempts at hydrolysis to remove the quaternary ethoxycarbonyl group proved to be disappointing and the product was recovered unchanged under even drastic conditions of acidic⁴ or alkaline hydrolysis (vide Experimental). This result was rather unexpected although Schinz *et al.*⁵ reported unusual difficulties in hydrolysing compounds of this type⁵. The keto-ester (VII) has now been obtained in a satisfactory yield through the catalytic reduction of the unsaturated keto-ester (VIII). The condensation product (IX) was hydrolysed and decarboxylated and the unsaturated keto-ester (VIII) was isolated in a satisfactory yield.

The saturated ester (VII) was allowed to react with methylmagnesium iodide and the hydroxy-ester so obtained was dehydrated to afford (II). This was hydrolysed to the unsaturated acid (X) and the latter subjected to ring closure in presence of zinc chloride-acetic acid-acetic anhydride according to Bachmann *et al.*⁶ The neutral material so obtained was found to be a complex mixture. It exhibited absorption bands at 5.76 μ (strong), 5.83

μ (strong) and 6.0 μ (weak) in the infrared. There was no absorption maxima in the ultra-violet region (220-260 $m\mu$) suggesting thereby that 6.0 μ band arose from the double bond and hence weak in nature. The band at 5.76 μ may be ascribed to a δ -lactone, a byproduct during cyclisation. The ketonic material was isolated through its semicarbazone and on repeated crystallisation, a semicarbazone melting at 190° was obtained. Infra-red studies of the regenerated ketone revealed the presence of a strong peak at 5.83 μ and a weak band at 6.0 μ and the structure (I) was suggested for the ketone.

3. Schinz *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **35**, 1752.

4. Stevens *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4072.

5. *cf. Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, **37**, 1223.

6. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, **13**, 325.

Homogeneity of the semicarbazone could not be definitely stated as the original derivative was a mixture and it required repeated crystallisation to raise the melting point to 190°. Although the structure (I), assigned to the ketone, contains tetra-substituted double bond and hence stabilised sufficiently by hyperconjugation, there is no reason *a priori* to reject the alternative structure (XI) in view of the fact that Bachmann *et al*⁶ obtained a mixture of ketones (XII) and (XIII) from the cyclisation of the unsaturated acid (XIV).

To throw further light on this point, it was decided to develop an unambiguous synthesis of the ketone (I) by an independent method where the position of the double bond would be fixed. With that end in view, the unsaturated diester (XV) was allowed to

undergo Dieckmann cyclisation in presence of dry sodium ethoxide⁷ and the resulting β -keto-ester was hydrolysed to afford the ketone (I). It was further characterised through a semicarbazone melting at 221-22°. The mixed melting point with the semicarbazone previously described (m. p. 190°) was found to be 203-206°. This definitely establishes that the ketone (I) described earlier is a mixture of (I) and (XI), elimination of proton having taken place from the intermediate (IXa) in both directions leading to (I) and (XI).

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Methyl-2-ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone (V).—Ethyl crotonate (40.2 g.) was added dropwise to a cooled solution of ethyl acetoacetate (54.6 g.) in ethanol (125 ml) containing sodium (8.9 g.). After half-an-hour it was refluxed for 3 hrs. when a curdy white precipitate separated. Ethanol was removed under suction, the residue diluted with ice-cold water, and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was slowly acidified with 6*N*-HCl (60 ml) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent, the diketo-ester on drying in vacuum solidified to needleshaped crystals (49 g.), m.p. 89°. A solution of the diketo-ester (III, 49 g.) in dry chloroform (85 ml) and PCl_3 (12.5 g.) was refluxed on a water bath for 3 hrs. The solvent was distilled under

7. Inhoffen *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1954, **87**, 642.

reduced pressure. It was cooled, diluted with excess of ice-cold water, and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed thoroughly with cold 2% NaOH solution and water until neutral and finally dried. On distillation, it furnished a colorless liquid (17.1 g.) having a fruity odour, b.p. 127-30°/7-8 mm. An ethanolic solution (45 ml) of the enol chloride, (IV, 15 g.) was hydrogenated in presence of 10% Pd-C catalyst (180 mg.). The calculated amount (2 moles) of hydrogen was consumed rapidly in 4 hrs. After being worked up in the usual way, the residue on distillation afforded a colorless liquid (11 g.), b.p. 113-14°/10 mm. which gave a deep violet coloration with ferric chloride, n_D^{20} 1.4610. (Found: C, 65.5; H, 8.5. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7%).

3-Methyl-2-ethoxycarbonyl-2-(γ -ethoxycarbonylpropyl)-cyclohexanone (VI).—The keto-ester (9.2 g.) was added dropwise to a cold suspension of powdered potassium (2 g.) under xylene (100ml) and kept overnight. It was then heated on a water bath till whole of the potassium dissolved. The colour of the solution turned deep brown. Ethyl γ -bromobutyrate (12g.) was slowly added to the warm solution which was further heated over a steam bath for 8 hrs. and then refluxed in an oil bath for 10 hrs. It was cooled and poured in water containing HCl (conc., 15ml). After separation of the xylene portion, the aqueous layer was once extracted with ether. The combined organic layers were washed and dried. The solvent was distilled under suction. The residue on distillation furnished initially the unchanged keto-ester (4 g.), followed by a sweet-smelling colorless liquid (5.9 g.), b.p. 148°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 9.0. $C_{16}H_{26}O_5$ requires, C, 64.4; H, 8.7%).

Attempted Hydrolysis and Decarboxylation of the Keto-di-ester (VI). (a) A solution of the keto-diester (5.9 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) was added to an aqueous KOH solution (5 g. in 34 ml) and the solution was refluxed for 25 hrs. and then acidified with an excess of HCl (dil). The acidic product, isolated in the usual way, was esterified with ethanol (35 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 3 ml). The neutral product was distilled; yield 3 g., b.p. 140-50°/0.4 mm (Found : C, 64.9; H, 9.4. $C_{13}H_{22}O_3$ (ketomonoethyl ester) requires C, 69.0; H, 9.7; $C_{16}H_{26}O_3$ (ketodiester) requires C, 64.4; H, 8.7%).

(b) A mixture of the keto-diester (2 g.), water (10 ml), glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and HCl (conc., 28ml.) was refluxed for 74 hrs. Acetic acid was steam distilled and the acidic product was isolated, esterified with excess of diazomethane (nitrosomethyl-urea 4g.), and finally distilled; yield 0.8 g., b.p. 145°/0.5-0.6 mm. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 8.6. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3$ (keto-monomethyl ester) requires C, 67.9; H, 9.4; $C_{14}H_{22}O_3$ (keto-dimethyl ester) requires C, 62.2; H, 8.1; $C_{15}H_{24}O_3$ (keto-methylethyl diester) requires C, 63.4; H, 8.4%).

4-Ethoxycarbonyl-3-methyl-2-(γ -ethoxycarbonylpropyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (IX).—Potassium (17.6 g.) was dissolved in an excess of butanol⁸ and the latter distilled until a solid appeared in the flask. This was then cooled to the room temperature and Hagemann's ester⁸ (85.6 g.) added in one lot with shaking, when the mixture turned deep red and finally to a yellow mass. After keeping for 15 mins., ethyl γ -iodobutyrate (130 g.) was added and the whole slowly refluxed in an oil bath for 12 hrs. The product was cooled, acidified with HCl (6*N*) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with 2% sodium bisulphite solution, 5% sodium carbonate solution and water. On distillation, it gave a forerun of the unchanged materials followed by a thick yellow product (82 g., 69%), b.p. 162-65°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 64.7; H, 8.3. $C_{16}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 64.8; H, 8.1%).

3-*Methyl-2-(γ -ethoxycarbonyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone* (VIII).—The above keto-di-ester (77 g.) was refluxed with an ethanolic solution of KOH (575 ml, 15%) for 8 hrs. The product was cooled and slowly acidified with HCl (conc., 110ml). It was filtered and ethanol removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure. On diluting the residual liquid with water and saturating with salt, an oily product separated. The aqueous layer was extracted twice with ether. After removal of the solvent, the residue was thoroughly dried in vacuum and esterified with ethanol (385 ml) and H_2SO_4 (35ml, conc.) by refluxing for 9 hrs. On distillation it furnished a greenish yellow liquid (39.3 g.), b.p. 153-55°/0.8 mm., λ_{max}^{alc} 243 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.08), n_D^{20} 1.4859. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 8.9. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 69.6; H, 8.9%). The red 2,4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone* was crystallised from ethanol in long needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 119°. (Found: C, 56.0; H, 5.9; N, 14.1. $C_{19}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires C, 56.4; H, 5.9; N, 13.8%).

3-*Methyl-2-(γ -ethoxycarbonylpropyl)-cyclohexanone* (VII).—The unsaturated keto-ester (VIII, 32 g.) was hydrogenated in glacial acetic acid (60 ml) over Pd-C catalyst (0.9 g., 10%). The catalyst was filtered and the solution worked up as usual. The reduced ester distilled as a colorless liquid (29.7 g.), b.p. 140-42°/0.5 mm. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 9.4. $C_{13}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 69.0; H, 9.7%).

1,3-*Dimethyl-2-(γ -ethoxycarbonylpropyl)-cyclohexene* (II).—The Grignard reagent, prepared from methyl iodide (11 ml) and magnesium turnings (3.6 g.) in dry ether (60 ml) was added with vigorous stirring over 50 mins. to a solution of the keto-ester (28.2 g.) in ether (150 ml) at -10°. Stirring was continued for about 3 hrs. till the reaction mixture attained room temperature. This was decomposed with HCl (dil.) and the ethereal layer separated. The aqueous phase was again extracted with ether. On distillation it gave a colorless liquid (22.8 g.), b.p. 140-55°/3 mm. This was dissolved in dry ether (125 ml) containing pyridine (14 ml). Thionyl chloride (7.5 ml) was next added dropwise to the ice-cooled mixture. It was kept at ice-bath temperature for 2 hrs. and then at room temperature for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was decomposed with HCl (dil.) and finally extracted with ether. On working up in the usual way it gave a mobile, brown liquid (17.4 g.) having a pungent smell, b.p. 132-37°/6 mm. Freshly prepared metallic copper (10 g.) was added to the solution of the above product in thiophene-free benzene (600 ml) and this was refluxed for 3 hrs. On filtration benzene was removed under suction. The residue on distillation furnished a colorless, mobile liquid (17.2 g.), b.p. 132-34°/6 mm. (Found: C, 74.6; H, 10.4. $C_{14}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 10.7%).

1,3-*Dimethyl-2-(γ -carboxypropyl)-cyclohexene* (X).—The unsaturated ester (17.2 g.) was added to an ethanolic KOH solution (17 g. in 113 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 6 hrs. On diluting it with water the neutral fraction (3.7 g.) was removed with ether and discarded. The aqueous layer was then acidified with HCl (conc.) and extracted with ether. The red viscous residue left on removal of ether afforded a colorless liquid (12.7 g.), b.p. 135-37°/0.6 mm. (Found: C, 73.1; H, 9.8. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.4; H, 10.2%).

6 10-*Dimethyl- Δ^5 -octalone* (I) and its *Bond Isomer* (XI).—A solution of the above unsaturated acid (4 g.) in acetic anhydride (40 ml) and a 5% solution of fused anhydrous zinc chloride in glacial acetic acid (12 ml) was allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 hrs. and then heated on a water bath at 70-80° for 40 mins. The wine-red solution was diluted with ether and shaken repeatedly with ice-cold 5% NaOH solution till acidic pro-

ducts were removed. The residue left after removal of the solvent was distilled at 88°/1.5 mm. The distillate had a camphoreaceous odour; yield 2.1 g.

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in presence of sodium acetate in water, was repeatedly crystallised from aqueous ethanol (1:1) in glistening button-shaped crystals, m.p. 190°. (Found : C, 66.2; H, 9.0. $C_{13}H_{21}ON_3$ requires C, 66.4; H, 8.9%.)

The ketone was recovered by refluxing the above semicarbazone (2.8 g.) with aqueous HCl (10 ml., 10%) for 2 hrs. The product on distillation furnished a colorless liquid (1.13 g.) having a camphoraceous smell, b.p. 104-105°/7 mm.

1,10-Dimethyl-5-keto- $\Delta^{1:9}$ -octalin (I).—1,3-Dimethyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-(γ -ethoxycarbonylpropyl)-cyclohexene (4.26 g., the details to be published elsewhere; cf. D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1959) was dissolved in dry benzene (80 ml) and treated with vacuum-dried sodium ethoxide (from sodium 0.53 g.). The reaction mixture on heating (nitrogen atmosphere) under reflux for 4 hrs. with brisk stirring turned into a deep brown homogeneous liquid. After thorough cooling, it was acidified slowly with HCl(dil.). The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with benzene. The combined organic extract was washed twice with water and the solvent removed. The red-coloured oil gave a deep violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride. The crude keto-ester was mixed with an aqueous 7% KOH solution (50 ml) and refluxed in nitrogen atmosphere for 12 hrs. After cooling it was diluted and acidified with HCl (20 ml, conc.) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was thoroughly washed with 10% sodium carbonate solution and water and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent the residue on distillation furnished a colorless mobile liquid (0.85 g.) having a camphoraceous odour, b.p. 117-119°/8 mm. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 221-22°. (Found : C, 66.3; H, 8.7; N, 17.8. $C_{13}H_{21}ON_3$ requires C, 66.4; H, 8.9; N, 17.9%)

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